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Summary report about data governance

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In 2024, several iterations followed version 1.0 of the core document and the appendices in follow-up telcoms and bilateral discussions. Version 1.1 was submitted as a Deliverable on the date stated in the DoA. Given the extension of the project and a new BOYD workshop at the end of it, the scientific officer asked to resubmit it with possible updates by the end of the project.

● Executive Summary

This Deliverable describes the governance of the HEAP Platform. The HEAP platform is a generic term for the tools developed during the HEAP project and allows for several use cases. A researcher or research institute could employ the HEAP platform as its research environment. However, that does not necessitate a specific HEAP governance. As explained in the HEAP sustainability plan (D1.2), the tools will remain available at the HEAP GitHub repository for as long as that site exists. As governance is, in essence, about the responsible and accountable balancing of the interests of various stakeholders, one specific research institution using HEAP tools is not relevant for a particular HEAP governance document. That research institution will have already organised its governance.

A very different use case is where a data holder on the one hand and a requesting researcher (affiliated with a research institution, other than the data holder) at the other end use the HEAP Platform, with all the tools already embedded in it as has been developed during the Project, and which is hosted at CSC. As the processor, CSC offers a secure data analytics environment with these HEAP tools. In that case, this data chain involves various responsibilities of each party, and a HEAP-specific governance document should give guidance. Hence, this document is about this specific use case

The responsibilities of the various entities involved in this data chain are described. It starts with a research protocol submitted by the requesting researcher. The data holder should approve that the requested data may be used for the intended research according to its own governance, including its commitment to the cohort participants or registry.

To make the HEAP Platform governance easily accessible to researchers, a split has been made between a concise core document and explanatory appendices. Appendices start with a letter explaining further legal arrangements that must be made between the data holder and the requesting researcher (via their research institution). Appendix 1 describes the Secure Processing Environment and the Five Safe principles. Appendix 2 discusses the governance literature about data-intensive research and justifies the choices made for the governance of the HEAP Platform.

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1 Introduction

The HEAP Platform at CSC provides a secure processing environment to analyse large and heterogeneous datasets, especially in the context of exposome research, amongst other things, via specific software tools developed during the HEAP project. Both during the HEAP project (ending on 30-06-2025) and thereafter, researchers other than the partners in the HEAP project can use the HEAP Platform, as the HEAP Platform will remain available for (exposome) research after the closing of the HEAP project.

As with any data-driven research, data assets and data analysis tools are subject to conditions. This document describes these conditions. According to the present discourse, those conditions are subsumed under 'the governance' of the HEAP Platform.

These conditions are the relevant legislation and major ethical norms that apply to data-driven research and the conditions that the HEAP partners have agreed upon for research via the Platform, which remain applicable after the expiry of the project.

Via these conditions, HEAP aims:

- To create the conditions for (exposome) research, which conforms with applicable data protection legislation (the General Data Protection Regulation, but also the national data protection legislation) and applicable ethical norms;
- To provide clarity to all (possible) users of the Platform under what conditions data can be processed via the Platform;
- To avoid 'research waste' by:
 - Opening up data from their silos,
 - Furthering the validation of the outcomes of the research,
 - Clear and not unnecessarily complex procedures¹;
- To achieve accountability for all stakeholders regarding exposome research via the Platform.

2 The use case for the HEAP Platform

HEAP assets, such as its contribution to specialised omics analysing software or the FAIRification of data², can be used by others under various

¹ See Appendix 1

² See the HEAP website: <https://heap-exposome.eu/>

circumstances. This governance document is about a specific use case where the data is analysed at a specialised central Platform created during the HEAP project by researchers throughout Europe.

Such a situation is the most complex from a data governance point of view.

3 Terminology

The obligations mentioned in this document are formally those of organisations, the legal entities. Those are represented by actual persons, in this case, the researchers. Those will arrive, usually together with researchers from other organisations, at a common idea about a specific research, will draft a grant application when necessary, bring the intended project forward through the institutional procedures such as a legal department, ethics committee, consultation of a data protection officer (DPO), the Board or head of department. This document abstains from the internal rules of an organisation. Those cannot be encompassed in a generic governance document applicable to all organisations. Only the main elements are mentioned, as external yardsticks must always be met.

As follows from the use case, this governance document is about a data chain. There is the original data holder or data source. That organisation has data that a research institution requests. When all the conditions are met, that data will be analysed at the HEAP Platform. The original data holder will usually be a research institution and will perform research with

the data internally, but that is out of scope in this governance document. When the data are made accessible to the requesting research institution, the latter will become a data holder of those data and the derived data as the results of the analyses. Sometimes the research institution requests data from one original data holder and merges those with data for which it is also the original data holder.

The different steps in the research data chain reflect different roles. Different legal obligations apply to each role. We need a terminology that distinguishes the role of the organisations in the various steps. The terminology should be neutral, only reflecting the organisation's role in the steps in the data chain. To those neutral terms, we can then ascribe responsibilities and legal roles.

- The original data holder is hereinafter referred to as ODH.
- The requesting research institution is referred to as RRSHI.
- The in-between phase, where the data are analysed, is in neutral terms referred to as the Platform.

As mentioned, in the research protocol phase, the ODH and RRSHI will be represented by the actual researchers working there. Only authorised researchers will be able to analyse the data on the Platform. But from a formal, legal point of view, the legal entities where they are employed remain the externally (towards supervisory authorities, funders, participants) responsible organisations, hence the ODH and the RRSHI.

4 Set-up of the governance document

We have structured the conditions (hence obligations and legal responsibilities) around three sections, reflecting the phases of the research in this use case:

- The input: under what circumstances may data be submitted to the Platform?
- The throughput: what research can be performed on the Platform under which circumstances?
- The output: what data may or even should leave the Platform and under which circumstances?

The practical conditions can be found in those sections. This distinction is only made to clarify different roles in light of the purpose of the Platform. In reality, the topics addressed in these sections are interconnected. All

data access should start with a sound proposal about the type of research that needs to be performed on the HEAP Platform. Hence, the intended output and the throughput influence the input.

Before addressing the specific roles and conditions, we discuss the principles guiding the HEAP Platform governance. This document would become too long if we were to give details about the legal documents to which ODH and RRSI will be bound. An overview can be found in the Appendices starting with a letter (A and following). The background information with a justification about the choices for this governance and more practical information can be found in the appendices starting with a number (1 and following).

5 Purpose and functioning of the HEAP Platform

As mentioned, the three topics must be seen in the light of the purpose of the Platform. This purpose can be described as:

To provide a secure processing environment (SPE, see [Appendix 2](#)) where data sources from various European countries can upload data for responsible exposome research and as such offers advantages for researchers compared to if the data were to remain in national silos by:

- Offering a collaborative environment with specialised research pipelines across different datasets for exposome research;
- Offering automated harmonisation of the data;
- Enabling the development and sharing of analysis tools;
- Offering a metadata catalogue that improves the findability of the data.

In addition, the platform offers an environment to store metadata, simulated or synthetic data with the pipelines to harmonise, enrich, and process or analyse the data, so that other researchers may try new approaches to handling the data before approaching the submitting researcher to analyse the data in, for example, a national SPE.

Hence, the basic assumption of the HEAP Platform is that it offers computational resources with tools for transparent and truly reproducible (exposome) research, which would be more challenging by other means, such as when data remain in their silos or when using a fully federated approach (example given via national SPEs and using "atashield like

methods"). Using AI to find new correlations between diverse data in the context of exposome research would exemplify the necessity of having well-curated data in one place.³

The HEAP Platform uses a semi-federated approach. Data from the ODH will only be uploaded to the Platform in the context of a specific research project, following the conditions described in the "input" section.

One of the input conditions is that the ODH that the data source contributes to the Information Commons (IC) of HEAP. That IC is not a personal data commons. It holds the metadata of cohorts and registries that can or have been analysed at the HEAP Platform and the metadata of the new datasets generated via the analyses on the Platform. The data commons is an essential element of the FAIR principles.

6 Principles of the HEAP data governance (using the HEAP Platform)

The starting principle is that the HEAP Platform comes to fruition with the ambitions for that Platform as described in section 1 of this document.

In the HEAP governance system, each ODH will always remain in control of whether data and what data can be analysed for research. In that system, adding a layer of control via a HEAP ethics or data access committee is unnecessary on top of what each data source should decide. Apart from the fact that a mandate by each data source to such an overarching committee is not easily feasible, that mandate tends to end with the project. At the same time, this document should remain applicable after the HEAP project, just as the HEAP Platform may be used after the project.

Requesting access to data at each original data source might be complex for the researcher as well, as experience has shown. Each data source will have its own rules and procedures for that decision based on the GDPR, national and institutional rules, and the provenance of data, including their commitment to the participants. This governance document, with the Appendices, helps by giving the tools to reach a faster decision.

³ Bak, Marieke, Vince Istvan Madai, Marie-Christine Fritzsche, Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, and Stuart McLennan. 'You Can't Have AI Both Ways: Balancing Health Data Privacy and Access Fairly'. *Frontiers in Genetics* 13 (2022). <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fgene.2022.929453>.

That relates to the technical aspects of the HEAP Platform as a SPE, as explained in Appendix 2. A SPE provides, insofar as relevant here:

- Secure access rules assuring that only recognised researchers can access the data and only to the data that they are authorised to have access to;
- The impossibility of downloading the original data. Only the results of the analysis can leave the Platform. This makes the data anonymous within the confines of the SPE.

The other help is by offering templates reflecting the GDPR principles, such as data minimisation and privacy by design. The researcher will need to justify why specific data is required. For example, synthetic data should be used if the research can be performed with these data.

7 The HEAP Platform and the European Health Data Space

The HEAP Platform is hosted by CSC, which hosts SPEs recognised by the Finnish state. In GDPR terms, CSC is the processor of all data processing performed on the Platform. The GDPR based controller-processor agreement can be found in [Appendix A](#). The user of the Platform is also bound by other basic rules of CSC. These and a short introduction can also be found in [Appendix A](#).

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) is an EU initiative to enable the secure sharing and use of health data across member states to support healthcare, research, and policymaking. Once fully implemented, the EHDS will significantly change the secondary use of health data. Notably, it will transition data analytics from local research infrastructures to Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) certified by EHDS-authorized entities. In addition, it seeks to facilitate cross-border data analysis through a harmonised approach that is accessible across Europe.

For exposome research, these developments offer several opportunities. The EHDS will enable cross-border data requests through the Health Data Access Body (HDAB). The HDAB of the country from which the data is requested will decide whether a data permit is granted or not. However, it will take time before the EHDS is implemented and operational for exposome research, namely March 26, 2029, and if genetic or (other) -omics data are involved, March 26 2031 (and -omics data are often involved in exposome research). Additionally, the EHDS will not be an exclusive route. Research cooperation outside the EHDS will remain possible. In sum, this governance document will remain relevant for using the HEAP platform in the coming years.

8 Roles and responsibilities in general

The HEAP Platform governance is centred around the following types of parties:

1. The ODH can make data available for exposome research.
2. The processor, which offers the SPE with the hardware and software tools to perform the research.
3. The RRSHI, with researchers who have drafted the research protocol, requests data from the data source to perform the research, and if the request is granted, will perform the agreed-upon research.

The practical roles of these parties lead to certain legal roles in terms of the GDPR and terms of civil law when a contract has been agreed upon. Those specificities for roles and responsibilities are further explained in the following sections, under the categories: input, throughput, and output. As mentioned, the various roles and responsibilities are interconnected, and cross-references are made in those sections. Sometimes, there are joint roles in GDPR terms, such as "joint controllers". Section 9.2 explains when that would be the case, with further guidance in Appendix B.

The HEAP consortium does not have a specific role beyond this governance document. The HEAP consortium facilitates or has facilitated (after the expiry of the project) cooperation between data sources and researchers by providing the necessary infrastructure. The HEAP Platform is set up together with the governance document so that when the HEAP project has ended, the Platform can still be used.

Appendix 2, zooming in on the governance discussion in data-intensive research, justifies the governance choices made for the HEAP Platform.

9 More about certain roles

9.1 Roles may coincide in one organisation

The ODH can also be the RRSHI or, more clearly, researchers within one organisation may request data assembled by researchers at another department of that organisation for a specific project. Other researchers in that organisation want to use this data for a new project. In that case, most responsibilities attached to the different roles (making data available when possible according to applicable norms and performing the research according to the research protocol) remain the same. The difference is that there will only be one controller in the sense of the GDPR, being that organisation with its different branches. Section 10 will delve deeper into the first role.

9.2 Joint controllers

As mentioned, legal roles are also attached to the content-wise roles (what functions in the research process). When data is exchanged between two different parties, they need to have entered into an agreement, as explained in section 8.

Parties also have roles under the GDPR. It was already mentioned that the middle party, hosting the HEAP Platform, is a "processor" in terms of the GDPR. The other parties are controllers.

The controller, in terms of the GDPR, is the entity that determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data. If entities determine purposes and means together, they are joint controllers. Appendix B delves deeper into that discussion.

The ODH is always the controller, at least till the approved dataset is used for research. In most cases, the ODH and the RRSHI will be joint controllers. Likewise, more research institutions will be joint controllers if they agree and cooperate in the study design and/or analyse the data together. [Appendix B](#) offers practical help and the elements for a joint controller agreement as follows from the GDPR.

Strictly speaking, "controller" and "processor" only apply when personal data is being processed. However, we propose to use this document and the appendices accordingly when anonymised data are being exchanged.

10 Input conditions

By input, we refer to the process of uploading data to the Platform. As mentioned, input, throughput, and output form a continuous cycle.

The intended output determines the research design and protocol (the throughput), which in turn specifies what data are needed as input.

A precondition for data to be used in research is that they must be findable. Therefore, every data source uploading data to the Platform is required to complete the metadata catalogue, even if a researcher has already discovered the data source independently and the catalogue entry is incomplete (i.e., still in the information commons). This requirement enhances transparency and ensures a level playing field for all researchers using the data. [Appendix C](#) provides the necessary information.

Uploading data to the HEAP Platform requires various steps:

1. A research protocol that has been approved at the requesting research institution.
2. The requested data can legitimately be used for the research, so the protocol must also be approved at the original ODH.
3. A data access agreement between the ODH and the RRSHI.
4. When applicable, a joint controller agreement.

5. A controller-processor agreement of each party (ODH and RRSHI) with the processor.
6. Pseudonymisation of the data by the ODH.
7. A further technical agreement between the data ODH and the processor about the secure, encrypted data transfer to the processor.

Ad 1:

All research should be based on a research protocol, which is the responsibility of the requesting research institution via the researchers involved. That protocol may have been discussed and negotiated in advance with the ODH (in which case, the data ODH and the RRSHI would be joint controllers). The research protocol should at least justify:

- Why will the intended research, in all likelihood, contribute to better prevention or treatment of specified groups of citizens or patients, or will it generate new hypotheses for further health research?
- How will the research results not become the proprietary knowledge of one or more parties, but will become publicly available to improve health care systems or our shared understanding of possible new avenues of research?
- The necessity and proportionality of processing the requested data for the research.

Ad 2:

This is the responsibility of the ODH. The data processing for this research should be compliant with the regulations for research with the data applicable at the data source. Those are the GDPR and national implementing legislation, the commitment to the participants of the cohort or registry who contributed to the data, and possibly other applicable rules for controlling that the data may be used for research, such as approval by an ethics or data access committee.

Ad 3:

In that data access agreement, the ODH guarantees that the data may be used for the purposes of the stated research, and the RRSHI guarantees that the data will only be used for the stated research. **Appendix B** provides further guidance, based on what is customary in European research cooperation and avoiding a 'battle of the forms' as much as possible.

Ad 4-5

Discussed already.

Ad 6

After this stage, the requested data is processed and transferred to the Platform. This relates to the following steps:

- Further advancing privacy by design by only transferring the data necessary for the approved research. These will be synthetic data if the research can be performed with these data.
- And by, at least, pseudonymisation of the data, or new pseudonymisation if the data were already pseudonymised.

ODH needs to perform these two steps.

Ad 7

This relates to the actual transfer. This is a practical step, but the "how this is done" needs a technical agreement between the data ODH and the processor.

11 Throughput conditions

At this stage, it should be ensured that authorised researchers will only use the data for the permitted research. Appendix A describes the legal aspects. The practical aspects of getting an account at CSC can be requested at CSC.

12 Output conditions

The output will be decided both in the DAA and via the throughput conditions of the Platform.

The results of the research must be published. The DAA covers the commitment of the research institution in this respect (see [Appendix B](#)). It is also part of the conditions for the processor to analyse the data on the HEAP Platform (see Appendix A).

The output is also new data. The results will lead to a new dataset. That new dataset will get a DOI. Unlike the published research, the new dataset will not be "pen data" It will usually be a dataset with sensitive personal data. This dataset must be made FAIR. Yet, access licenses will apply as follows from the applicable governance (the conditions in the approvals) before generating the dataset.

13 Transparency

This is a shared responsibility.

The ODH should make it transparent that the data are being used for this specific research. How this is done will very much depend on the governance of the ODH. It is not necessary to inform all participants individually, insofar as that can be done, unless that would be part of the governance and commitment towards the participants. Other options would be a general newsletter or a website. Data sources that cannot offer this transparency cannot participate in research enabled by the HEAP Platform. The transparency should be guaranteed in the DAA.

Likewise, the RRSHI should make transparent what research it performs and is required to publish the results.

14 Costs

14.1 In 2024

During the lifetime of the HEAP project, the following applies:

- The Platform can be used for free by any researcher at an RRSHI wanting to process data for research.
- Partners in the HEAP consortium carry their own costs in making data available for research via the Platform, regardless of whether the RRSHI is a HEAP partner or not.
- Non-HEAP partners who want to make data available for research via the Platform:
 - Carry their own costs for making data available if they perform research with their data on the Platform (data source and research institution coincide), or;
 - If another research institution requests the data, the data controller and the research institution will make an agreement in the data access agreement about the costs for making the data available.
- These (possible) costs shall only be the actual additional costs of the data source in making the data available (e.g., those of a data manager).

14.2 After 2024

After the lifetime of the HEAP project:

- The processor may charge the research institution for the data processing involved in the research.
- The data ODH may charge costs to make the data available via the Platform.
- These (possible) costs shall only be the actual additional costs of the ODH in making the data available (e.g. costs of a data manager) and the actual costs of the processor.
- If Hopsworks software updates are needed, Hopsworks may charge costs for these updates.

15 Concluding remarks

With this governance document and the Appendices, the HEAP consortium has contributed to a sustainable use of the central HEAP Platform generated during the project as of 2025. The document builds on the earlier work of WP 2, 6, 7, and 10.

In 2024, certain aspects of Appendix B were reviewed in collaboration with the legal departments of the HEAP partners and the Ethical Advisory Board. After refining the technical tools developed by other work packages, the complete governance document was tested during two BYOD workshops. None of the participants objected to the decentralised assessment approach, and consequently, no one identified a need for a separate HEAP data access committee.

It should be emphasised that this document does not limit the use of the HEAP resources to access through the Platform alone. There are additional use cases for the HEAP acquisition.⁴ The software tools developed in WP5, WP6, WP9, and WP10 of HEAP and the ideas and concepts described in this document can also be applied outside the central Platform. These tools can be integrated into the research environments of individual institutes for their own studies, whether focused on exposome research or other fields. Similarly, this document's underlying ideas and concepts can be implemented in a wide range of projects, regardless of whether they relate to exposome research.

⁴ see the HEAP website for that acquis.

16 Appendix A

CSC offers a model controller-processor agreement (meeting the European standards for such an agreement)

<https://research.csc.fi/data-processing-agreement>

and other conditions for using the Platform

<https://research.csc.fi/general-terms-of-use>

Summary: Use of services is intended for (Finnish) academic research⁵ and only for the purposes for which the services have been granted. Research results should be released publicly. General rules on account management, the responsibilities of the user and what a user will not do, the responsibilities of the project manager and the user's responsibilities for the content that is stored in or transmitted via the services.

<https://www.csc.fi/en/data-policy>

Summary: purpose of the policy and the data management principles (Data ownership is clear and management responsibilities agreed upon; Data are documented and their lifecycle defined; Data publicity and protection are managed appropriately; Data are made as open and as interoperable as possible; Data management solutions favor open standards, protocols and software; Data management competencies.

⁵ The text states Finnish, but researchers from other countries can use the services as those have been developed during HEAP as well. For example, CSC has a long-standing relationship with the Swedish Karolinska Institute. In the future, it might be that using the HEAP platform at CSC will be mediated by Karolinska, as the former coordinator of the HEAP project, in order to lower the administrative burden for CSC. Karolinska will, in that case, only perform administrative functions. The authors of this document will not have any legal role as a processor or controller in the envisioned project unless those parties agree otherwise.

17 Appendix B (Joint) controllers and the Data Access Agreement between the ODH and the RRSHI

17.1 Summary

For the original data holder (ODH) to give access via the Platform to the approved data to the researchers from the requesting research institution (RRSHI), a data access agreement (DAA) is necessary. It is proposed to combine this DAA with a joint controller agreement. Recent case law has affirmed that one is easily considered a controller in the sense of the GDPR: "natural or legal person who exerts influence over the processing of personal data, for his, her or its own purposes, and who participates, as a result, in the determination of the purposes and means of that processing, may be regarded as a controller in respect of such processing."

Formally, that controller will be the organisation where the researchers are employed. In practice, it will be researchers at the ODH and the RRSHI who come to terms about the research and the necessary data, and then submit this to the various bodies (DPO, ethics committee, perhaps legal department, etc.) who will give advice or give an authorisation that the research may be performed.

If agreed with the ODH, it might be upheld that a data holder that only gives access without any further involvement in the protocol is not a controller for the research data.⁶ The processing at the ODH to make the data available is not done for its own purposes but solely for the purpose of the RRSHI. However, usually there is some kind of meaningful interaction or influence together with the researchers from the RRSHI before the data is released. The ODH makes the purpose of the research its own as well. That makes the ODH also a controller for the research data. ODH and RRSHI are then joint controllers for the research data. Joint controllership will also exist when several research institutions have decided on the research protocol.⁷ Article 26 GDPR obliges joint controllers to meet certain criteria. One element is a joint controller agreement (hereinafter: JCA). As explained in the next section, it is difficult to meet some other elements of those criteria for the research institution in the research data chain where the research

⁶ (Becker et al., 2021; Van Veen et al., 2022)

⁷ In federated systems, where the questions are brought to the data, the standard clauses for a joint controller agreement are even more inapt. The requesting research institution will only retrieve certain statistical output from the source database. Yet, because of defining the research and at least agreeing with the means, it is controller or joint controller with the source database and depending on the governance probably also a joint controller with other researchers in the network.

institution only receives pseudonymised data. The ODH, on the other hand, can meet those other criteria. An agreement that combines the DAA with the JCA would simplify matters to a large extent.

17.2 Joint controllers with pseudonymised data

- a. As seen, in the case of joint controllers, article 26 of the GDPR obliges a JCA. It should be mentioned that a JCA is not constitutive for being joint controllers. Whether parties in the research are joint controllers or not, is decided upon the factual circumstances, mainly being the amount of influence on the data processing for the purposes of the party.
- b. The obligations of the GDPR concerning joint controllers are in sum:
 - i. The JCA should, in a transparent manner, determine the respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under the GDPR, in particular as regards the exercising of the rights of the data subject and their respective duties to provide the information referred to in Articles 13 and 14;
 - ii. The JCA may designate a contact point for the data subjects;
 - iii. The JCA must duly reflect the respective roles vis-a vis the data subject;
 - iv. The essence of the JCA must be made available to the data subjects.
- c. There are several examples of Joint Controller Agreements (JCAs) available online.⁸ However, these examples often fail to consider that controllers in a research data chain may not have access to directly identifiable data and are, in fact, prohibited from attempting to re-identify data subjects, even if technically possible. In this context, the research data chain means that the ODH only provides researchers with pseudonymised data.
- d. It should be emphasised that these specific features of the research data chain exist for good reason, as they align with key principles of the GDPR, including data proportionality, data minimisation, and privacy by design.
- e. For a research institution at the other end of the data chain, article 11 GDPR is applicable.
- f. In summary, the article states that:
 - i. If the controller neither possesses nor needs directly identifiable data about a data subject, they are not required to obtain

⁸ [Model Joint Controllership Agreement_EN.docx \(live.com\)](#); [Template-GDPR-Joint-Controllership-Agreement.docx \(live.com\)](#); Template for Joint Controller Agreement of collaboration, e.g. ERA-NET Cofund Actions and European Partnerships.

- additional information solely to fulfill GDPR obligations toward the data subject;⁹
- ii. In such cases, the articles concerning the data subject's rights to access, erasure, information, etc., do not apply unless the data subject provides additional information that enables their identification.
 - g. Article 11 solves a paradox. To comply with the GDPR, the controller needs to interact with the data subjects, but as seen, for the (joint) controller at the pseudonymised data end of the data chain, it cannot. According to article 11, it does not need to make efforts to re-identify the data subject to do so (efforts that are forbidden in the DAA anyhow).
 - h. Hence, point iv of number b does not need to be met on an individual basis by each of the joint controllers. But it does need to be met by a controller who can meet that obligation, which would be the ODH

17.3 A side step to transparency in the governance document as a linking pin

The HEAP Platform governance document emphasises that research conducted using the Platform must be transparent. Both data holders and research institutions share responsibilities in this regard. The Platform itself, which processes the data, remains neutral in this respect.

The GDPR also requires transparency, particularly under Articles 13 and 14, although these obligations can often be formalistic and not genuinely meaningful for participants. According to Article 11, the GDPR's transparency requirements do not extend to RRSHI entities further downstream in the data chain; however, transparency in governance remains essential (see Appendix 2 on governance).

In cases involving joint controllers, a Joint Controller Agreement (JCA) is mandatory, and there will always be a Data Access Agreement (DAA) within the data chain. The essence of the JCA must be made available to data subjects, as part of the formal GDPR transparency obligations. However, this cannot be done by the research institution, since it typically only knows the categories of data subjects (i.e., the sample provided by the data holder) rather than their identities, and the data subjects may also reside in different countries.

⁹ This paraphrases the text of article 11.1 GDPR. The text states: 'for the sole purpose of complying with this regulation'. The GDPR still applies, such as data security or being a joint controller or not. But Chapter III of the GDPR, the rights of the data subject, cannot be complied with as, to put it simply, the controller does not know who that data subject is. See also point g in the text.

17.4 Combining those elements in a combined DAA/JCA.

The following does not apply in the rare case where the data holder takes a completely neutral stance on whether the data will be made available for research and/or is not involved at all in the subsequent research. Only in such cases would the ODH not be considered a joint controller with the RRSI. However, these situations are expected to be rare.

In the majority of cases, we recommend combining the Data Access Agreement (DAA) with the Joint Controller Agreement (JCA), for the following reasons:

- Both agreements pertain to the same data — the research data released by the data holder — as other data parties are not joint controllers.
- They address the same responsibilities and obligations: the data holder's legitimate release of the data for the specified research, and the research institution's obligation to use the data solely for that research.
- They involve the same obligations toward data subjects. Only the data holder can fulfill these obligations (see Article 19 GDPR), and national implementations of Article 89(2) GDPR may also be relevant.
- They concern the same processor.
- They are subject to the same applicable law, conflict resolution provisions, etc.
- Although this interconnection could be achieved through two separate agreements that reference each other (with the DAA as the parent agreement), a single combined agreement would be clearer and more understandable for both researchers and the boards of data holders and research institutions, which ultimately need to approve these agreements.

17.5 Broad lines of the combined DAA/JCA

In the following, we give some general guidance about the clauses of the joint DAA/JCA. Despite decades of European cooperation, a universal EU¹ template still does not exist. All DDAA's are project-specific.

However, there are always common elements. Items marked with an asterisk (*) indicate additions from a JCA perspective.

Common clauses:

- Two or more parties, being a:
 - Data holder (s)
 - Data requester(s), the research institution(s), often called Recipient(s)

- To what is given access: data (further detailed in Annex 1)
- Permitted use: the research proposal (further detailed in Annex 2)
- Guarantee of the data source that the data may be processed for the intended use by the researchers:
 - If the data subject revokes consent or uses the right to erasure, insofar as applicable, the data holder will remove the data from the dataset.
 - Compliance with article 16(3) GDPR
 - When applicable, incidental findings will be reported back to the data holder
- Transparency by the data holder that the data are being made available for research under a JCA*
- Guarantee of the research institution that data will only be used for the intended research by the assigned researchers
- The assigned processor
- Researchers are prohibited from attempting to re-identify data subjects
- No warranty that the data are indeed suitable for the intended research
- Publication
- Acknowledgement of data sources
- Liability and Indemnity
- Applicable law
- Annexes describing:
 - The research
 - The data
 - The researchers' access rights

On applicable law:

Outside of EU-funded research consortia, the choice of applicable law can become complex due to the so-called 'battle of forms,' where each party prefers their own national law. Within EU-funded consortia, the applicable law is typically defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA), and parties can simply refer to these. However, outside this framework, no such fallback exists.

A practical proposal is to designate Belgian law and Belgian arbitration as the governing framework for the agreement. This is often acceptable because all parties have usually participated, at least in part, in consortia that included such clauses and are familiar with this arrangement.

18 Appendix 1: SSPE's

A Secure Processing Environment (SPE) is a computing environment built for the processing of data types, often called sensitive data, that require an increased security level. Tightening regulations in Europe on privacy and health data management are driving the development of these environments. These data types typically cover health data, registry data, or other statistical data. The term originates from the European Data Governance Act:

"The physical or virtual environment and organisational means to ensuring compliance with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular data subjects' rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, ensuring compliance with applicable Union and national law, and allowing the entity providing the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including to display, storage, download, export of the data and calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms",

Data Governance Act (DGA), EU regulation 2022/868

Besides technology and software, SPEs comprise processes to provide a secure environment for sensitive processing accessible remotely for authorised users. From a technology point of view, typically, SPE security measures include secure login (e.g., multi-factor authentication), role-based access rights, and data encryption. SPEs, together with appropriate robust and independent accreditation, monitoring, and auditing processes, improve public and data subjects' trust in providing access to their data for research.

Secure Processing Environment is one part of the wider concept of Trusted Research Environment (TRE) that specifies to whole ecosystems of safe research on health data. Implementations of TREs in the UK are mostly in regional health care organisations that de-identify their data and allow qualified researchers access to all of it in their own SPE.

Trusted Research Environment builds on the Five Safe principles [1]. The "Five Safes" framework is a set of principles used to manage the risk associated with the use of sensitive data for research. Risk is addressed by complementary adjustments on the implementation of each "Safe" to provide an appropriate context for research to occur while maintaining an optimal balance between research benefit and overall risk management.

Five Safes builds on the following dimensions (UK Health Research Alliance, 2021):

- Safe projects: Is this use of the data appropriate, lawful, ethical, and sensible?
- Safe people: Can the user be trusted to use it in an appropriate manner?
- Safe data: Does the data itself contain sufficient information to allow confidentiality to be breached?
- Safe settings: Does the access facility limit unauthorised use or mistakes?
- Safe outputs: Is the confidentiality maintained for the outputs of the management regime

Groos and van Veen expanded this concept to 6 safes, namely, also 'safe transit' as the first step, and forwarded that if the safe output only allows anonymous data as the publishable statistical results of the research, the data processed for the research can be considered anonymous data (Groos & Veen, 2020).

The EHDS seems to indicate that SPEs will only allow the output of such data. CSC supports such a system but also supports other types of output, with other means for output control.

19 Appendix 2: Governance in context

19.1 Introduction, scope and set-up of this Appendix

This Appendix explains the choices made in the HEAP Platform governance document. Governance is a broad term with different meanings given to it, depending on the context. Those meanings are hardly ever made explicit. We will first explore the concept of governance as that has its origins in the literature on public administration and since then has been expanded to other domains.

The recent governance literature is highly normative. Governance of a certain social phenomenon as an object of study about how this governance works, is mixed with normative ideas about how the actors involved in that phenomenon should operate, in short, good governance by those actors. Often the focus is exclusively on the latter. That means an infusion of ethical ideas or principles about such good governance.

Those ethical ideas or principles are not fixed but subject to continuous debate. Some of those principles are aspirational and are the result of a – sometimes difficult to entangle – mix of assumptions that those can work in practice with value judgements that these principles should work in practice. The value judgments are based on principles of autonomy or if not, at least a kind of 'controllability' of the individual, perhaps mediated by intermediary organisations. Those organisations can take different forms, from 'data cooperatives' to privacy advocate groups who claim to act in our interest.

We will briefly discuss the majority of those publications and explain why the HEAP Platform governance took a less aspirational approach. We submit that this approach is still ethically correct. Though it may not be fully aligned with the mainstream academic governance discourse, it is fully aligned with an undercurrent of data solidarity and responsible use of data for public health, which is exposome research.

19.2 Defining governance

The concept of governance has been developed in political theory as a reaction to changes in political practices. (Kjaer, 2004) These changes range from top down control by the nation state via 'regulation' to increasing fragmentation of 'steering' or political power by global or regional networks beyond the nation state, the influence of international organisations and non-governmental bodies, and within the nation state, decentralisation, the closer interaction with civil society and citizen's involvement in policymaking. (Levi-Faur D. (ed.), 2012).¹

Many publications when using the term governance are applications of this kind of research agenda; how is a certain issue governed, such as the governance of biomedical research.² Yet, there are also more practical definitions, namely about how organisations such as public bodies set the rules in relation to its subjects. The distinction between the research approach and this more practical approach, can be subsumed as 'governance of' versus 'governance by'. With the discussion on 'governance by' come normative elements how this should be done, in short increasing legitimacy, efficiency-, democracy and accountability.³ In 2008, the Council of Europe elaborated on this, with 12 principles for (good) governance by local authorities. The principles include issues such as ethical conduct, responsiveness, rule of law, efficiency and effectiveness, transparency, sound financial management and accountability.⁴

The term governance has spread and for example is also use for 'data governance'. An often-used definition reads: *the exercise of authority, control, and shared decision-making (planning, monitoring, and enforcement) over the management of data assets"*.⁵ Yet, such a sort of value neutral definition misses that the biomedical governance discussion has been infused with normative elements. We will come back to those but first briefly explore the governance of and governance of and governance by interface.

19.3 Governance as co-governance by non-governmental actors

In the discussion of (good) governance by state actors, the state actors still make the binding decisions though an increasingly complex environment of supra state regulations, more horizontal relations with the subjects, agencies and supervisory authorities, spokespeople of civil society and ultimately sometimes corrected by the judiciary.

Governance by non-state actors will always be bound by the rules set by statal actors, whether supra national as Regulations by the EU or national. It is within the open space left by the regulators that governance by non-state actors can take place. Yet, there might also be a mutual dependency. The better the non-state actors take their role in good governance by, the less necessity there will in principle be for regulators to fill in gaps for (possibly) socially unwanted performance by the non-state actors. Hence, this governance by non-state actors should be seen as co-governance.

Within this open space, co-governance is filled in with principles of *good* governance. However, the space is not really that empty. In between state regulations, including international treaties, and the internal rules of research institutions, there is an abundance of non-formally binding recommendations, guidelines, declarations (usually written in capitals) and the like by non-state organisations such as the World Medical Association⁶, or international organisations with a hybrid character, such as CIOMS⁷.

There is multi-level governance after Follesdal et al., when it was still called multilevel regulation (Follesdal, Andreas et al., 2008). Criticism of the multilevel governance especially by non-democratically appointed or publicly accountable bodies beyond the pure technical norms (insofar as these would not also have normative or societal impact) and this – after Vibert – rise of the unelected (Vibert, 2007) have been raised (Follesdal, Andreas et al., 2008; Smith & Weinstock, 2019; van Veen, 2018) regarding its procedures and, specifically for the WMA Taipei declaration, also its outcomes (Ballantyne & Eriksson, 2019).

In spite of these critical observations, co-governance by research institutions must also navigate through that muddy terrain of quasi-legislation or international soft law which constitute their governance of. However, as they are not binding, there is more latitude to deviate if this can be explained and sufficiently justified.

19.4 Governance "b" in biomedical research

There is an abundance of papers in biomedical journals (including journals dedicated to ELSI aspects of such research) which discuss the legal, ethical and social (ELSI) norms which big data and -omics research should follow. We may refer to reviews by (Kalkman et al., 2019) for data intensive research in general and to that of (Safarlou et al., 2023) specifically for exposome research. Papers specifically about governance by research institutions build on the main elements of responsible research following from those papers but with different accents. In the governance documents we took certain elements but also took a moderate, one might even say "grass root" approach.

With this approach the HEAP governance distances from Muller et al. claiming that "learning governance" should be established at the network level (Muller et al., 2022). Though some of the criticism of the existing situation via "consortium agreement governance" is correct, it completely misses the point that networks are by definition not a legal entity which can make decisions *and* that many research networks overlap with the same actors involved⁸. Their "solution" of instituting a "data intensive health research network governing bod" would lead to a multitude of such bodies on top on of governance bodies at the level of data sources or research institutions requesting data. The added value of such on top of, hence extra layer of research vetting, is explained by referring to very generic and, though lofty, rather elusive and hence difficult to summarise principles. Such on top of can also be seen as "research waste" after the contribution of Salman et al. in the special issue of the Lancet of already 2014 on research waste (Salman et al., 2014). It might not be "on top o" if the network governance body would be mandated to decide instead data sources and requesting research institutions. But apart from the fact that

one cannot mandate a network or even a consortium as that is not a legal entity, as already mentioned, the mandate and the means to sustain a body expire after the project ends. Overarching data access committees do not survive (Murtagh et al., 2018) the funding of a project and why should such a network governing body. More importantly, Muller et al. do not explain why citizens would be helped by being addressed by or being able to address that European plethora of overlapping research network governing bodies instead of being able to do that at home, the data sources or the research institutions of their country.

Networks come and go but that data and the custodians behind those, remain as well as the researchers wanting to use those data. Hence, the position taken in the HEAP governance document. The responsibilities are laid or brought back, if you wish, to those levels of the grassroots where the data are assembled which can be made available for research, or the research institutions requesting those data. Each of those will be accountable for doing the right thing in interaction with their stakeholders ranging from the participants who contributed data at the data sources to funders and many others in between.

Based on that starting point, the governance document stipulates the conditions which must be met to use the HEAP Platform. These conditions reflect main elements of the "governance b" discussion. The data processing is seen in the light of the research protocol which as mentioned in the first dot at section ... of the core document, should justify why the intended research would in principle on the shorter or longer run (the latter especially when it is more fundamental research) to better health prevention or treatment of specified groups of the population. We summarise that aim as "reasonable public health research" (see hereinafter).

The rebuttal might be threefold.

The first is that though the governance document allures to the necessity the social value of research, it does not take a stance on that participants should have the ultimate say which data may be used for which research as advocated in some of the literature (Kaye et al., 2015; Ploug & Holm, 2016). Indeed, the governance document is neutral on further refinements which by the way have never been implemented in a sustainable way in practice. We see the data in the light of responsible public health research ((Ballantyne, 2019) and do not immediately agree with the present 'mydata' approach. For a criticism on that approach see (Ballantyne, 2020; van Veen, 2022). However, this does not mean that data sources which did take that approach, cannot open-up data via the HEAP Platform. It only means that data sources which did not, can open-up data via the HEAP Platform as well.

The second rebuttal might be that "reasonable public health research" is not operationalised any further. There is a long and complex debate about public health research, even with anonymised data, and its consequences for certain groups in the population as summarised in D.2.2 of the HEAP project. Here again the governance document is relatively neutral. Funders, researchers dependent on that funding and data sources will in the European context find a balance which might not be perfect but which in the European system of the rule of law can always be challenged.

The last potential rebuttal would be that there is no total oversight mechanism. What if the research protocol would be sloppy and the data source would agree to that? Apart from a general observation that the perfect can be the enemy of the good, the good being in this case that data will not be locked up in their silos, there is oversight already though not "overarching total". Together with the condition set out in the core document, at the grassroots of both ODH and RRSI (and their funders), there are sufficient mechanisms that the research will be sound and responsible from a data protection perspective, and in a broader sense, towards the participants who directly or indirectly contributed with data and (European) society as a whole.

20 Appendix 3: description of the HEAP Reference Architecture

In Figure 1 we illustrate the HEAP Reference Architecture and its components as single instances, however considering the need for a distributed system, we mention that the Information Commons, Knowledge Engine, Metadata Warehouse and Entitlements Management System components can be scaled to multiple instances. The Submission Engine layer will be able to submit data to any of the instances of the Information Commons.

Each of the layers utilises a different color in order to set them apart, or as in the case of the data sources and primary user groups to illustrate that they are representing similar concepts. The arrows illustrate a direct connection between the primary user groups and a certain layer.

As the system needs to handle heterogeneous data sources and in some cases even raw data, before the data could be part of the HEAP Information Commons component it needs to be harmonised. This is achieved through extraction, transformation and loaded (ETL) jobs created as part of the Submission Engine component. Therefore this requires a dedicated layer and is positioned on top of the data sources.

The data can be on-demand stored in the IC. This implies that the data can remain at its source, and is provided to the IC only when it is required for analysis. The data will be tailored to the analysis and can include pseudonymised data.

Once the data is made available in the IC, it is only accessible through theHEAP'ss Knowledge Engine (KE). The mechanism for accessing the data from the IC is via OAuth 2 and the apparatus for providing access is described in section 2.3 Authorisation and Authentication. Entitlements Management System is the software that registers the data access requirements and keeps track of the researchers that requested data access and the data authorisations.

The Knowledge Engine provides the tools and interfaces for the implementation and integration of scientific analysis workflows as bioinformatics pipelines. It provides means for applying AI (as Machine learning and Deep learning) to analyse, mine, produce and validate hypotheses and associations to extract actionable knowledge from the data. The resulting information (the knowledge as a sum of data, metadata or features etc.) is represented in the Metadata Warehouse and is available for sharing and reuse along with associated metadata, thus making it also findable - ultimately enabling the platform to be FAIR compliant.

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